

Cloning and Analysis of Fusarium Wilt Resistance Gene Analogs in ‘Goldfinger’ Banana

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Molecular Pathogens 2010, Vol 1 No 1 DOI: 10.5376/mp.2010.01.0001

Received: Sep. 29, 2010

Accepted: Oct. 26, 2010

Published: Oct. 30, 2010

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Preferred citation for this article as:

Sun et al 2009, Cloning and Analysis of Fusarium Wilt Resistance Gene Analogs in ‘Goldfinger’ Banana, Molecular Plant Breeding, 7(6): 1215-1222

Abstract Based on the conservative regions of the nucleotide-binding site and the leucine-rich repeat (NBS-LRR) in cloned wilt resistance genes, the polymerase chain reaction with degenerate primers was employed to isolate resistance gene analogues (RGAs) from the genomic DNA of wilt resistance germplasm ‘Goldfinger’ (AAAB) banana. As a result, twenty fragments of RGAs were isolated, which were of expected size (about 530 bp). Analysis of the deduced amino acids of these RGAs show that they share the NB-ARC domain and belong to the non-TIR-NBS class resistance gene candidates, containing 4 conservative amino acid domains, i.e. P-loop (GMGGVVGKTT), Kinase-2 (LLVLDDIW), RNBS-B (CKVLFTTRS), and hydrophobic amino acids GLPL (GLPLALKVL). Other results reveal that sequence identity among the 20 RGAs rang from 41.1% to 99.3%, while identity of the deduced amino acid sequences range from 33.2% to 96.3%. The phylogenetic analysis of the RGA nucleotide sequences and the deduced amino acids showed that the 20 sequences could be divided into 5 distinct types. All of the amino acids deduced from the RGAs share a homology of 28%~54% with those deduced from the known wilt resistance genes such as Fom-2, I2C-1, I2C-2 and I2. This result to some degree indicates the conservation of disease resistance gene evolution. Technically, these RGAs isolated in the present study would lay a base for the further cloning of wilt resistance genes in banana, which could also be used as molecular markers for screening candidate wilt resistance genes in banana.

Keywords Banana, Fusarium wilt, Resistance gene analogs, Nucleotide binding site

Background

Banana (*Musa* spp.) is one of the most important fruit crops in the world in terms of production and consumption. Fusarium wilt is regarded as one of the most devastating diseases of banana, affecting plantations in almost all banana-growing countries of the world (Ploetz et al., 1990). This disease is caused by the soil-borne fungus *Fusarium oxysporum* formae specialis (f. sp.) cubense (FOC) (Stover, 1962). The fungus, surviving as chlamydospores, will germinate to infect the lateral or feeder roots when they come into contact with banana roots (Beckman, 1990). After infection, the pathogen will colonize and block the plant's vascular system, a process that leads to wilting, and eventually, plant mortality (Ploetz and Pegg, 2000). In recent years, Race 4 of this fungous pathogen (Foc4) has become the most virulent race of this disease. It can infect almost all the banana and

plantain cultivars, including those that were resistant to other races of the disease (Ploetz, 1993).

The most common cultivar in worldwide commercial production is the Cavendish cultivar, which has resistance to some isolates of FOC (Pegg et al., 1996). Commercially grown banana plants, which are clonally propagated, sterile triploid plants, are highly susceptible to Fusarium wilt due to many factors (Pegg et al., 1996; Vuylsteke, 2000). Although plant micropropagation leads to the reduction in the spread of FOC, it also results in enhanced susceptibility to FOC for two years after plantlets are removed from tissue culture (Smith et al., 1998). Options for the control of Fusarium wilt are limited by ineffectual chemical control and the lack of commercially suitable resistant cultivars (Smith et al., 2006). And no known fungicide is effective in controlling FOC4 up to now. Hence, the development of new banana

cultivars resistant to this disease, FOC4 in particular, holds the key to the successful control of this disastrous disease in banana production.

Unfortunately, cultivated banana varieties are mostly triploid and can only be propagated asexually, making it difficult to improve this crop genetically using conventional plant breeding methods that rely heavily on cross-pollination between plants. As an alternative, the introduction of resistance genes into banana plants via biotechnological means offers a valuable way of developing resistant banana cultivars (Sagi, 2000). To date, however, no R gene/s capable of conferring resistance to FOC4 has been reported. One potential source of Fusarium R gene/s is the 'Goldfinger' (AAAB) banana breed in Honduras showing strong resistance to diseases, especially to race 1 and race 4 of *Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *cubense* (Foc) (Pegg et al., 1996). This kind of banana, therefore, potentially represents an important source of Fusarium R genes for molecular breeding.

The largest class of R genes encodes proteins with a nucleotide-binding site (NBS) and a leucine-rich repeat (LRR) domain. The NBS-LRR genes are unevenly distributed between chromosomes, several being clustered as local multigene families (Meyers et al., 1999). The NBS-LRR class can be divided in two subclasses, the TIR and the non-TIR, depending on the presence of a domain at the N-terminus with homology to the *Drosophila* Toll and mammalian Interleukin-1 receptors (TIR) (Meyers et al., 1999). Non-TIR-NBS-LRR genes are present in both monocot and dicot plants, whereas TIR-NBS-LRR genes appear to be restricted to dicot plants (Meyers et al., 2003; Zhou et al., 2004).

According to the conservative regions of the nucleotide-binding site and the leucine-rich repeat (NBS- LRR) in cloned wilt resistance genes, the polymerase chain reaction with degenerate primers was employed to isolate resistance gene analogues (RGAs) from the genomics DNA of wilt resistance germplasm 'Goldfinger' (AAAB) banana. Twenty fragments of resistance gene analogues (RGAs) were isolated, which were of expected size (about 530 bp). The availability of these sequences opens the

possibility of applying different strategies for their functional analysis and for developing disease resistance in this crop.

1 Results

1.1 RGCs of the NBS-type from banana

Twenty fragments of resistance gene analogues were isolated from 'Goldfinger', which were of expected sizes (about 530 bp). Analysis of their deduced amino acid sequences revealed the presence of the typical NBS motifs of R genes in the spatially correct locations, leading to the conclusion that all the 20 RGAs, designated GF1~GF20, were resistance related gene analogs associated with fusarium wilt in banana. Sequence identity among the 20 RGAs ranged from 41.1% to 99.3%, while identity of their deduced amino acid sequences ranged from 33.2% to 96.3%. The comparison between the deduced amino acids sequence of banana NBS/LRR resistance gene analogues in GenBank (EU123872) and those of GF3, GF7, GF11 and GF18 showed a sequence identity of 93%, 87%, 93% and 88%, respectively, while the remaining 16 banana NBS resistance gene analogues in this study shared 38%~65% amino acids homology with other R genes. The results indicate that banana NBS resistance genes belong to multigene families.

1.2 Sequence comparisons of banana RGCs with other R genes

Analysis of the deduced amino acids of these RGAs showed that their domain structures were NB-ARC and belonged to non TIR-NBS-class resistance gene candidates, containing 4 conservative amino acid domains of P-loop (GMGGVGGKTT), Kinase-2 (LVLDDIW), RNBS-B (CKVLFTRRS) and hydrophobic amino acids (GLPLALKVL) (Figure 1). The N-terminal regions of the banana RGCs showed no sequence similarity to the TIR domain, suggesting the RGCs of this species belong to the non-TIR-NBS-LRR type like other monocot R gene and RGC sequences. Similarity searches of the protein databases also revealed that each RGC showed significant similarity to RGCs isolated from other monocots such as *Oryza sativa*, *Saccharum officinarum* and *Avena sativa* as well as some known non-TIR-NBS-LRR resistance genes. The 20 RGAs showed approximately 28%~54% sequence identity to Fom-2, I2C-1, I2C-2, and I2 which confers resistance to *Fusarium* in *Cucumis* and *Lycopersicon*.

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MP2010, Vol.1, No.1 <http://mp.sophiapublisher.com>

GF1	..GEVGRKIMV.R.KV.FN.....DGKW.....IKDHFQPIRAWL.V.YV.SDNFNV...ER.DST...YMN.RLTK...SEHSMIIF.SAFFN	65
GF2	GMGGVGRITLA.K.LV.YN.....D.Q.....RIKDYHQV...WVTK.FSDNENVHSMRR.I.II...DAS.NENLQ...EK.....	58
GF3	GMGGVGRITLA.Q.LI.YO.....D.KRV.....ERFHQ...LRI.RCCLGVSFDLG...EI.LKAI...SRGTGRSDLFKFMMD.L...	62
GF4	GMGGVGRITLA.S.KI.YN.....D.W.....IKDHFQPIRAQK.WLYI.....SK.DYT...EIK.LREL...IRCAQDET.KSLLV	60
GF5	GMGGVGRITLA.P.KI.YN.....D.G.....WIRVNEPKPRI.WLYV.....SK.QVFDLQHEII.VKAG...DTVKGFFS.KEQLV	64
GF6	GMGGVGRITLA.S.KI.YN.....E.R.....IIQQAWLYV...KNKE.MIGDVGKTCDAK.SFE...GES.RAELE...PKLASLLT.ENLF	68
GF7	GMGGVGRITLA.Q.LI.YN.....D.KRV.....ERFHQ...LRI.WVCVSGEGFD...EI.LR.IT...KEATGRSDLFKFMMD.L...	61
GF8	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.YN.....D.E.....RIKDYHQV...WVTK.FSDNENVHSMRR.I.II...DAS.NENLQ...EK.....	52
GF9	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.YN.....D.D.....WLENIRVITSQK.FS.....EIQLLEII.ASSFG...DTRDQ.S.RSEQL	59
GF10	GMGGVGRITLA.RPKI.FN.....D.E.....RIKENFLRA...WLECV.....SQ.EES...ETD.IEQI...IREAEVNY.RE...	56
GF11	GMGGVGRITLA.S.KI.YI.....N.KRV.....ERFHQ...LRI.WVCVSGVFDLG...EI.LKAI...SSATGRSDLFKFMMD.L...	61
GF12	GMGGVGRITLA.RPKI.FN.....D.E.....RINEFYSKD...VV.....SQ.EES...ETD.IEQI...IREAEVNY.RE...	53
GF13	GMGGVGRITLA.P.KI.YN.....D.G.....RIKDYHQV...WVTK.FSDNENVHSMRR.I.II...DAS.NENLQ...EK.....	54
GF14	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.YN.....D.E.....RHFQNYPIRA...WVVCV.AYENFDETKTK.NYS...ETD.LKEM...IVNYRE...	62
GF15	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KV.FN.....D.S.....RIENEFPIRA...WLCV.....TK.NYS...ETD.LKEM...IRCAQDET.KAVE	56
GF16	GMGGVGRITLA.Q.HA.YN.....D.W.....IKDHFQPIREKV.WLYV.SDNFNV...ER.DST...YMN.RETKEIESEHSMIIF.SAFFN	69
GF17	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.YN.....D.E.....RIKDYHQV...WVTK.FSDNENVHSMRR.I.II...DAS.NENLQ...EK.....	51
GF18	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.E.....ERFHQ...LRI.WVCVSGVFDLG...EI.LKAI...SSATGRSDLFKFMMD.L...	61
GF19	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.E.....WTKENFLRA...WVCV.....SO.EES...ETD.IEQI...IREAEVNY.RE...	55
GF20	GMGGVGRITLA.Q.HA.YN.....D.KRV.....IKDHFQPIREKV.WLRQ.SDNFNV...ER.DST...YMN.RETKEIESEHSMIIF.SAFFN	71
I2	GMGGVGRITLA.K.AV.YN.....D.ERV.....KNHFQ...LKA.WFCV.SEGFDA...LR.IT.KE...ELQEIKGFSKDVHN...	59
I2C-1	GMGGVGRITLA.K.AV.YN.....D.ERV.....QKHFQ...LKA.WFCV.SEAEDA...FR.IT.KG...ELQEI GSTDLKADDN.LNQLQ	64
I2C-2	GMGGVGRITLA.K.AV.YN.....D.ERV.....QKHFQ...LTA.WFCV.SEAEDA...FR.IT.KG...ELQEI GSTDLKADDN.LNQLQ	64
Fom-2	GMGGVGRITLA.K.LV.FS.....H.ELV.....RQHFQ...KTV.WVCVSEPFIVN...KI.LLDIL...QSLKGGISNGGDSKEVL...	63
L6	GMGGVGRITLA.K.AV.YN.....K.I.....SSCFDCCCFIDN.IRET...QE.KDG...VVV.LQKLVSEILRIDSSGVGFNND	64
M	GMGGVGRITLA.K.AV.YN.....K.I.....SSHFDRCCCFIDN.VRAM...QEQRDG...IF.I.LQKLVSEILRMD...SVQFNND	63
N	GMGGVGRITLA.R.AI.FD.....T.LLQMDSSYQFDACFKD.IKE...KRG...MHS.LQNALSELLREKAN...Y.MNE	64
P1B	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.E.....FTIMRPFILVE.LLRS.LAEQLH...KG.SSK.KELENNRV...SS	66
PRF	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.VHA...QCVVQIOLYSWRE.LLTL.LLNDVL...EP.SDR.NEK...58	58
RPP1	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.VHA...QCVVQIOLYSWRE.LLTL.LLNDVL...EP.SDR.NEK...58	58
RPP5	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.VHA...QCVVQIOLYSWRE.LLTL.LLNDVL...EP.SDR.NEK...58	58
RPS2	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.VHA...QCVVQIOLYSWRE.LLTL.LLNDVL...EP.SDR.NEK...58	58
RPS5	GMGGVGRITLA.R.KI.FN.....D.VHA...QCVVQIOLYSWRE.LLTL.LLNDVL...EP.SDR.NEK...58	58
Xal	GMGGVGRITLA.Q.LV.CK...DLVIK...SOFNVKIW.V.YV.SDKFDV...VK.ITR...QIL.DHVVNSHEGIS...66	66
RPM1	GMGGVGRITLA.A.NIFKQSVRRHFE.SYA...WVTK...S.VYIEDV...FR.TMI.KEFYKADT...67	67
GF1	VKGEQSR.S.NNFDITLQDEKLSKRFL...FL.VLDVWWT.D.W.D.RFRAPLOY.GEP...GSK.I.LVITRIRKIAEMVGNF	135
GF2	...ETQKGF...LL.VLDVWRA.DR.Q.VW.EDLKALL.TSN...CR...I.VVITRIRNENVARNMGN	108
GF3	...QCSVRDVLAKRYL...L.VLDVWNE.DSSKW.D.DLRALLC.GGD...GSR.V.VVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	122
GF4	TRAESFEO..ESRAELPKLASLLTENL...FL.VLDVWVSP.KV.W.T.DELRPLQ.GEP...GSKRTI.LVITRIRKIVLSOVKAS	133
GF5	TRVVS...ESTNKF...LL.VLDVWWT.AV.W.T.DELRPLS.KGE...GS.RTI.LVITRIRVLSMMGT	121
GF6	...L.VLDVWNE.DP...I.FW.DDLRPLR.CGD...GSK...I.LVITRIRKIVARMGTPL	112
GF7	...L.VLDVWNE.DSSKW.D.DLRALLC.GGD...GSR.V.VVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	121
GF8	AESFEO..ESRAELPKLASLLSKRL...FL.VLDVWVSP.YV.W.N.DELRPLS.KCG...GDSR.I.LVITRIRVLSOMKAS	122
GF9	PMLRR...AIEGPF...LL.VLDVWRA.DV.W.N.DELRPLS.KCG...GD.SRI.LVITRIRVLSOMKAS	116
GF10	...AT..ERAQLVQTRVVSLLSTNS...LI.VLDVWVA.DV.W.D.DLLRNPLO.SGV...ANDSRI.LVITRIRVLSOMKAS	123
GF11	...QCSVRDVLAKRYL...L.VLDVWNE.DSNEYD.DLKALLC.GGD...GSR.V.VVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	121
GF12	...AT..ERAQLVQTRVVSLLSKRL...LI.VLDVWVSP.NV.W.T.DELRPLS.KCG...S...I.LVITRIRVLSOM...	114
GF13	AESFEO..P...KLQEDLASLLTKL...FL.VLDVWVSP.NV.W.T.DELRPLQ.GGA...AGRS.I.VVITRIRVLSOMK...	119
GF14	...RAELPKVLSLLSRNL...LL.VLDVWVSP.DV.W.E.N.LLRNPLP.DNG...SK...I.VVITRIRNIAIOLGN	122
GF15	GA..ESRAELPKVLSLLSRNL...LL.VLDVWVSP.DV.W.EVBLRNPPLS.SAM...AASNCI.LVITRIRNENVARNMGN	124
GF16	VKGEQSR.S.NNFDITLQDEKLSKRFL...L.VLDVWNE.DSLEK.W.E.RECAPLKH.GEP...GSK...I.VVITRIRNENVARNMGN	127
GF17	VESLGL..VSRSELEPKLASLLTKML...FL.VLDVWVA.TV.W.N.DELRPLS.KGV...GSR.I.LVITRIRVLSOMKAS	121
GF18	...QCSVRDVLAKRYL...L.VLDVWVSP.NSSKW.D.DLKALLC.GGD...GSR.V.VVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	121
GF19	...AT..ERAQLVQTRVVSLLSTNS...LL.VLDVWVA.DV.W.D.DLLRNPLO.SGV...ANDSRI.LVITRIRVLSOMKAS	122
GF20	VKGEQSR.S.GVFDITLQDEKLSKRFL...L.VLDVWNE.DSLEK.W.E.RECAPLKH.GEP...GSK...I.VVITRIRNENVARNMGN	143
I2	...N.LNQLQVLLKESLQKRF...L.VLDVWNE.NYNEW.N.DLRNIFAQ.GDI...GSK...I.IVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	124
I2C-1	VKLKADDN..LNQLQVLLKESLQKRF...L.VLDVWVND.NYEPW.D.DLRNIFAQ.GDI...GSK...I.IVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	136
I2C-2	VKLKADDN..LNQLQVLLKESLQKRF...L.VLDVWVND.NYEPW.D.DLRNIFAQ.GDI...GSK...I.IVITRIRSDGVSSMGTL	136
Fom-2	...LRELOKEMEGQTYF...L.VLDVWNE.NSFLQW.E.LKYCLLKI.TGN...SKN...SIVVITRIRSAEVAKIMGT	125
L6	SGGRKTIKERVSRFKILV...L.VLDVDEK.FK.F.E.DMLGSPKD.FIS...OSKFI.I.TSRMIRVLSRLENQC	127
M	SGGRKTIKERVSRFKILV...L.VLDVDEK.FK.F.E.DMLGSPKD.FIS...OSKFI.I.TSRMIRVLSRLENQC	126
N	EDGKHQMASRLRKKVLL...L.VLDVDEK.FK.F.E.DMLGSPKD.FIS...OSKFI.I.TSRMIRVLSRLENQC	126
P1B	KKSLASME..DITLQGLKRLKESLQKRF...L.VLDVDF.SD.ISEWQ.Q.IKPLFL.LEK...ISR...I.IVITRIRNENVARNMGN	137
PRF	...E.DGELADELRFLETKRFL...L.VLDVWVND.YKVD.N.LCNC.FSD.VSN...RSR...I.IVITRIRNENVARNMGN	121
RPP1	ISHLGVQAEQLRDKKVLV...L.VLDVDEK.FK.F.E.DMLGSPKD.FIS...OSKFI.I.TSRMIRVLSRLENQC	122
RPP5	IEHFQVVEQLRDKKVLV...L.VLDVDEK.FK.F.E.DMLGSPKD.FIS...OSKFI.I.TSRMIRVLSRLENQC	120
RPS2	VGARLGLS...WDEKTEGENRALKIYRALRQKRF...L.VLDVWVND.EID...L.E.KTGVPRP.REN...CKK...V.MFITRIRNENVARNMGN	122
RPS5	IGELKGLVGNWNEKNNQRAIDHNVLRKRFV...L.VLDVWVND.EID...L.E.KTGVPRP.REN...CKK...V.MFITRIRNENVARNMGN	122
Xal	...NLDITLQDEKLSKRFL...L.VLDVWVND.EID...L.E.KTGVPRP.REN...CKK...V.MFITRIRNENVARNMGN	130
RPM1	PAELYSLO..YRELVEKLEVEQSKRYI...L.VLDVWWT.TGLWR.E.ISTAL.FD.GIY...OSR...V.MFITRIRNENVARNMGN	127
GF1	F..PLGV...L...DDASYWEF...FKQAFGSEYAGECP...RKIVR...KCI...GLPLALKV	178
GF2	V...HHH...EE...MDEECGWEL...LWKT.VWVDN...KYNGEYEAIEGK...MVQKCDGFLPALKV	175
GF3	TT.HKLA...F...LSEE...D...SWDLFRFRAPP...DDKQHQNLVLEIG.RGIVTKCG...GFPLALKV	144
GF4	Y..MHA...EK...MDDNSQWML...AGEEDDMRRL...YP...RKIVRKC...CDGFLPALKV	179
GF5	LT.MHA...EK...MDDNSQWMLLQKTVFEAGEEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	149
GF6	Q..CWL...E...DAFVQSEP...WAKM.IVKNM...LKG...GLPALKV	175
GF7	NEQIRMA...F...LSEE...D...SWDLFRFRAPP...DDKQHQNLVLEIG.RGIVTKCG...GFPLALKV	169
GF8	Y..MHA...EK...MDDNSQWMLLQKTVFEAGEEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	170
GF9	Y..MHA...EK...MDDNSQWMLLQKTVFEAGEEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	174
GF10	Y..MHA...EK...MDDNSQWMLL...GK...EEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	174
GF11	TT.HKLA...F...LSEE...D...SWDLFRFRAPP...DDKQHQNLVLEIG.RGIVTKCG...GFPLALKV	162
GF12	Y..MHA...E...MDDNSQWMLLQKTVFEAGEEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	172
GF13	Y..MHA...EK...MDDNSQWMLLQKTVFEAGEEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	174
GF14	V...HHV...ELLPMDEECQEV...FOAE...DHRE...KODISVFK.EIGTK...MVQKCDGFLPALKV	176
GF15	V...HHV...EK...MDEECGWEL...LWKTVDHRE...KODISVFK.EIGTK...MVQKCDGFLPALKV	187
GF16	F..HRVK...L...LRKM...F...FKQAFGSEYAGECP...LKDVQFKIV...KCD...GLPALKV	174
GF17	Y..HQV...EK...MDDNSQWMLLQKTVFEAGEEDDMRRL...KEI.RKIVRKC...HGLPALKV	174
GF18	TT.HKLA...F...LSEE...D...SWDLFRFRAPP...DDKQHQNLVLEIG.RGIVTKCG...GFPLALKV	179
GF19	Y..MHA...EK...MDDNSQWMLL...GK...EEDDMRRL...EEV.RKIVRKC...DGFLPALKV	168
GF20	F..HRVK...L...LRKM...F...FKQAFGSEYAGECP...LKDVQFKIV...KCD...GLPALKV	189
I2	Q..IRMG...N...LSTE...A...SWSLFRHAF...ENMDPMGHPLEEV...G.RQIAAKCH...GLPALKV	176
I2C-1	A..IYMG...N...LSTE...A...SWSLFRHAF...ENMDPMGHPLEEV...G.RQIAAKCH...GLPALKV	188
I2C-2	Q..ISMG...N...LSTE...A...SWSLFRHAF...ENMDPMGHPLEEV...G.RQIAAKCH...GLPALKV	188
Fom-2	PG.HLLS...K...LSSD...H...CWSLFRHAF...ENMDPMGHPLEEV...G.RQIAAKCH...GLPALKV	188
L6	K..LYEV...GSMKPRSLLEFSKHAFKKNTPPSYVETLANDVVDITTA...GSMKPRSLLEFSKHAFKKNTPPSYVETLANDVVDITTA	173
M	K..LYEV...GSMKPRSLLEFSKHAFKKNTPPSYVETLANDVVDITTA...GSMKPRSLLEFSKHAFKKNTPPSYVETLANDVVDITTA	173
N	I..IYEV...TALPDHESIQLFKHAFKKNTPPSYVETLANDVVDITTA...GSMKPRSLLEFSKHAFKKNTPPSYVETLANDVVDITTA	178
P1B	NGNVHNLKVLKHNDAACL...LSEK...V...FEATYLDQNNPVLKVAEKILKCC...DGFLPALKV	175
PRF	SDPHHLRFLRFDWILL...QKEV...F...QOESC...PEL...EDVQFISKS...CRGFLPALKV	175
RPP1	HV...YKV...GYPNDFAQIFQCFMNAFQKPHQEGFDEISREVMALAG...EPLPALKV	193
RPP5	...YEV...KLPSQGLALKMISQYAFGKDSPPDFKELAFEAELVG...EPLPALKV	171
RPS2	YKLRVEFLKQHWELFCQKVPKDLLE...SSSIRRLA...EIVVS...KQ...GLPALKV	172
RPS5	NFMEISCLDTONAWDLKLVKVOENTLGS...HFDIPQLA...RKVSE...KCCFLPALKV	172
Xal	OSIKLEA...L...KDDIWSLFRHAFGNDKHD...SSPQLVGL...KQIAS...ELKGNPLAA	167
RPM1	GSTKHEITELKEDAWVL...FSNK...A...FPA...SLEQCRQNL...EPIARKLVERCQGLPALKV	172

Figure 1 Alignment of the deduced amino acid sequences of the NBS regions of 20 RGAs of 'Goldfinger' NBS sequences and selected non-TIR-NBS-LRR R genes known to confer disease resistance

1.3 Phylogenetic relationships of the banana RGCs

The phylogenetic analysis for RGA nucleotide sequences and the deduced amino acids revealed that the 20 sequences could be divided into 5 distinct types (Figure 2). All of The amino acids deduced from the RGAs shared homology (28%~54%) with those deduced from the known wilt resistance genes such as Fom-2, I2C-1, I2C-2, and I2 which indicate the conservation of disease resistance gene evolution. Technically, these RGAs isolated in the present study would lay a base for the further cloning of wilt resistance genes in banana. And they could also be used as molecular marker for screening of candidate wilt resistance genes in banana.

2 Discussion

Resistance (R) genes in plants play a crucial role in disease prevention. Many R genes are dominant, or incompletely dominant, and require specific dominant avirulence (Avr) genes in the pathogen for their function (Flor, 1946). This genetic interaction between plant and pathogen led to the current view that such R genes encode receptors for Avr gene-dependent pathogen molecules (Staskawicz et al., 1995). Upon recognition of these molecules, R gene products activate plant defense mechanisms. These defenses include rapid production of an oxidative burst resulting in cell wall cross-linking, localized cell death (the hypersensitive response), salicylic acid biosynthesis, and induction of genes characteristic of systemic acquired resistance (Levine et al., 1994; Ward et al., 1991). R genes have been shown to encode two broad categories of leucine-rich-repeat (LRR) proteins that can be distinguished by protein domain structure and site of pathogen perception (Jones and Takemoto, 2004). The NBS-LRR-containing R proteins mediate the recognition of an intracellular pathogen-derived signal. Thus far, NBS-LRR proteins have been shown to function in resistance signaling only in response to pathogen. The second category of R proteins is inserted in the plasma membrane and minimally consists of an extracellular LRR domain and a transmembrane (TM) domain (Jones and Takemoto, 2004).

Many studies suggested that there were three main relationships between RGA and resistance genes.

Figure 2 Phylogenetic tree of Musa RGAs and know plant R genes based on NBS domain

First, RGA is part of R gene or pseudo gene. In Arobidopsis, a sort of RGA was tightly linked with Rpp5 and was proved to be part of Rpp5 (Kanazin et al, 1996). Second, RGA was tightly linked with R gene. For instance, RGA were found to be tightly linked with different located R genes in rice (Nori et al., 2001). Third, RGA is unrelated to target gene. For example, some RGA did not link with located R-genes

in lettuce (Di Gaspero et al., 2002).

Several features of the banana putative RGCs isolated in this study suggest they are non-TIR-NBS-LRR disease resistance genes. For example, the characteristic motifs of the NBS domain of known resistance genes described (Meyers et al., 1999; Pan et al., 2000; Peraza-Echeverria et al., 2008) are present in each banana RGC at similar positions. One of these motifs, the highly conserved P-loop, has been shown to bind ATP in the NBS-LRR resistance proteins I2 and Mi from tomato (Tameling et al., 2002), suggesting the banana RGC proteins may also bind ATP. The non-TIR (nT) motif (Bai et al., 2002), which is associated only with the non-TIR subclass of NBS sequences, is found in the N-terminal region of the banana RGCs, while none of the motifs associated with the TIR subclass are found in the corresponding region of the banana RGCs. All of the amino acids deduced from the RGAs shared homology (28%~54%) with those from the known wilt resistance genes such as Fom-2, I2C-1, I2C-2 and I2. Among them, the homology between GF7 and I2 are relatively high (about 54%), which indicated that it might be a possible function of resistance to Fusarium wilt of banana.

3 Materials and methods

3.1 Plant material

'Goldfinger' (*Musa* spp., AAAB) plantlets resistant to

FOC subtropical race 4 (Smith et al., 1998) were obtained from South Subtropical Crop Research Institute, Chinese Academy of Tropical Agricultural Science, and were maintained in a phytotron at 28°C. Roots were harvested from 4-month-old plants, frozen in liquid nitrogen and then stored at -80°C for use.

3.2 DNA extraction

DNA was extracted from plant tissue using a modified CTAB method based on Doyle and Doyle (1987). Fresh root tissues (2~3g) were ground to powder and transferred to the extraction buffer [2% (w/v) CTAB (cetyltrimethyl-ammonium bromide), 1.4 mol/L NaCl, 20 mmol/L EDTA, 100 mmol/L Tris-HCl (pH 8.0) and 2% (v/v) β-mercaptoethanol]. The suspension was extracted twice with equal volume of chloroform:isoamyl alcohol (24:1). Dried pellet was dissolved in an appropriate volume of double distilled sterile water.

3.3 Degenerate Primers Design

According to the conservative regions of the nucleotide-binding site and the leucine-rich repeat (NBS-LRR) in cloned wilt resistance genes, five pairs of primers were designed to isolate R gene analogues (RGAs) from the genomic DNA of wilt resistance germplasm 'Goldfinger' (AAAB) banana (Table 1).

Table1 Degenerate primers used in amplification

NBS name	Peptide	Primer sequences encoded (5'→3')	References
F1(F)	P-loop	GGDGTDDGGNAARACWAC	Deng et al., 2000
F2(R)	GLPL	AANGCHAGNGGYAANCC	Deng et al., 2000
F3(F)	P-loop	GGWATGGGWGGWRTHGGWAARACHAC	Lee et al., 2003
F4(R)	GLPL	ARNWYYTTVARDGCVARWGGVARWCC	Lee et al., 2003
F5(F)	P-loop	GGIGGIGTIGGIAAIACIAC	Peraza-Echeverria et al., 2008
F6(R)	GLPL	AAGIGCTAAGIGGIAAGICC	Peraza-Echeverria et al., 2008
F7(F)	Kinase	GTNYTNGAYGAYGTNTGG	self-designed
F8(R)	Kinase	TAGTTGTRAYDATDAYYYTRC	self-designed
F9(F)	P-loop	GGNGGNRTIGGIAARACIAC	self-designed
F10(R)	GLPL	GAGGGCNARNGGNAIACC	self-designed

Note: Codes for mixed bases: R=A/G, W=A/T, M=A/C, K=G/T, Y=C/T, S=C/G, H=A/T/C, D=A/T/G, V=A/C/G, B=C/G/T, N=A/T/G/C, I=hypoxanthine

3.4 PCR and cloning

PCR mixtures (50 μL) contained 5 μL 10×buffer

(TaKaRa with MgCl₂), 4 μL 2.5 mmol/L dNTP, 1 μL of each degenerate primer, 5 U Taq polymerase

(TaKaRa), 1 μ L DNA, and then added ddH₂O to 50 μ L. Cycling conditions were performed as follows: Hot start; initial denaturation at 95°C for 3 min, then followed by 35 cycles each with denaturation at 94°C for 45s, anneal at 52°C for 30s, and elongation at 72°C for 60s, with a final elongation step of 72°C for 10min. Gel-purified amplicons were cloned into the plasmid pGEM-T Easy vector (Promega) and transformed into *Escherichia coli* JM109 competent cells following the manufacturer's instructions. Plasmids were extracted using the High Pure Plasmid Isolation Kit (TaKaRa).

3.5 Sequence analysis

All the cloned transformants were sent to Shanghai Sangon Biological Engineering Technology & Services Co., Ltd. for sequencing. Then the sequences were assembled and edited using the DNAMAN 5.2.9 Demo version software. Similarity searches were performed with the BLAST program (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov) using the default settings. Predicted protein sequences were aligned using the ClustalX 1.81 Program. A phylogenetic tree was constructed by the neighbor-joining method implemented in the Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) software with the Poisson correction.

Acknowledgement

This research was supported by the National Public Welfare Scientific Research Institution Foundation (SSCRI200714, SSCRI200804) and the Hainan Provincial Natural Science Foundation (No.807039)

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